

Effect of Post-Induction Treadmill Exercise on Hippocampal Agrin and Laminin in a Rat Model of Alzheimer's Disease: Relevance to Hippocampal Sclerosis

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Abstract

Background: Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common cause of dementia. Exercise is a practical and cost-effective intervention with neuroprotective effects. We examined whether four weeks of moderate treadmill exercise alter hippocampal levels of two extracellular-matrix (ECM) proteins—agrin and laminin—implicated in synaptic stability and blood–brain barrier function and considered the relevance to hippocampal sclerosis (HS) as a co-pathology in late-life dementia.

Methods: Male Wistar rats (n=24; 8 weeks) were assigned to A β 1–42-injected (A β), A β + exercise (A β +Ex), or control groups (n=8/group). After 7 days to allow early AD-like pathology, the A β +Ex group completed 4 weeks of treadmill running (5 days/week; weeks 1–2: 2 \times 15 min at 10 m/min; weeks 3–4: 2 \times 15 min at 15 m/min). Spatial learning and memory were assessed using the Morris water maze (MWM) and probe trial. Hippocampal agrin and laminin levels were quantified post-training.

Results: Compared with A β rats, A β +Ex showed higher hippocampal agrin and laminin levels ($p \leq 0.001$), and both A β and A β +Ex differed from controls (agrin: $p \leq 0.006$ and $p \leq 0.003$, respectively). Exercise partially normalized ECM protein levels and improved MWM performance.

Conclusion: Post-induction treadmill exercise modulates hippocampal agrin and laminin in an AD rat model, supporting ECM-mediated mechanisms of cognitive benefit. Given prior links among ECM remodeling, neuronal loss/gliosis, and HS in aging and epilepsy, these findings may have relevance to hippocampal sclerosis, although HS pathology was not directly assessed here.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease; aerobic exercise; A β ; agrin; laminin; hippocampal sclerosis